

Appendix B: Sample properties and spectral extraction

The JOYS sample consists of 20 low-mass protostellar systems, see summary of their main properties in Table B.1. The observations of NGC 1333 IRAS 4A and Ser-emb 8(N) do not cover the central protostellar position itself and are therefore excluded from the analysis of this paper, leaving a sample of 18 protostars. Table B.1 also indicates the total exposure time divided over the three MIRI-MRS gratings, as well as the number of dither positions. It is important to note that several observations included multiple pointings (i.e., B1-c, L1448-mm, IRAS 4B, BHR71-IRS1) covering parts of their extended blueshifted outflows. Furthermore, also toward some sources with a single pointing the center of the FOV was placed toward the blueshifted outflow

(i.e., TMC1A). However, given that only the spectra from the central protostellar position are covered here, only the pointings containing the central protostellar system are listed in Table B.1.

The list of coordinates from which apertures were extracted is also listed in Table B.1. Two sources, NGC 1333 IRAS 4B and Ser-S68N-S, do not show any MIR continuum and therefore spectra were extracted from the millimeter continuum positions (van Gelder et al. 2020; Tychoniec et al. 2021). The full extracted spectra and continuum images at $5.3 \mu\text{m}$ (channel 1 short), $8.1 \mu\text{m}$ (channel 2 short), $12.5 \mu\text{m}$ (channel 3 short), and $19.3 \mu\text{m}$ (channel 4 short) are shown in Figs. B.1-B.18 for all sources.

Table B.1. Sample of low-mass JOYS sources and their main properties in the PID 1290 JWST GTO program.

Source	RA J2000	Dec J2000	d pc	L_{bol} $L_{\odot}$	T_{bol} K	Class	Dithers	Exposure time s	Refs
B1-a-NS	03:33:16.69	+31:07:55.10	293	2.3	115	I	2	600	1,2
B1-b	03:33:20.35	+31:07:21.35	293	0.23	157	I	2	600	1,3
B1-c	03:33:17.90	+31:09:31.86	293	5.0	48	0	4	8000	1,2
L1448-mm	03:25:38.88	+30:44:05.64	293	8.5	49	0	2	600	1,2
Per-emb 8	03:44:43.99	+32:01:35.56	321	4.5	45	0	2	600	1,2
IRAS 4A ⁽¹⁾	–	–	293	14.1	34	0	2	600	1,2
IRAS 4B	03:29:12.02 ⁽²⁾	+31:13:08.03 ⁽²⁾	293	6.8	28	0	2	600	1,2
Ser-emb 8(N) ⁽¹⁾	–	–	436	1.8	–	0	2	600	3,4
Ser-S68N-N	18:29:48.13	+01:16:44.51	436	6.90	58	0	2	600	3,5
Ser-S68N-S	18:29:48.09 ⁽²⁾	+01:16:43.30 ⁽²⁾	436	6.90	58	0	2	600	3,5
Ser-SMM1-A	18:29:49.79	+01:15:20.37	436	109	39	0	4	600	3,5
Ser-SMM1-B	18:29:49.66	+01:15:21.16	436	109	39	0	2	600	3,5
Ser-SMM3	18:29:59.31	+01:14:00.65	436	28	38	0	2	600	3,5
SVS 4-5 ⁽³⁾	18:29:57.61	+01:13:00.12	436	38	–	I/II	2	600	5,6
L1527	04:39:53.84	+26:03:10.18	142	1.6	60	0/I	2	3000	2,7
TMC1-E	04:41:12.73	+25:46:34.64	142	0.7	161	I	2	600	2,7
TMC1-W	04:41:12.69	+25:46:34.63	142	0.7	161	I	2	600	2,7
TMC1A	04:39:35.21	+25:41:43.76	142	2.7	189	I	2 ⁽⁴⁾	600	2,7
BHR71-IRS1	12:01:36.50	-65:08:49.40	200	14.6	68	0	2	600	8,9
BHR71-IRS2	12:01:33.96	-65:08:47.78	200	1.7	38	0	2	600	8,9

Notes. The coordinates are those of the mid-IR continuum peak. The exposure time is the total exposure time divided over the A,B,C gratings for the pointing from which the spectrum was extracted. ⁽¹⁾ The pointing of IRAS 4A and Ser-emb8(N) was not centered on the protostar itself but offset on blueshifted outflow. ⁽²⁾ Coordinates for the millimeter continuum peak since mid-IR continuum is not detected. ⁽³⁾ SVS4-5 is a Class I/II sources that is behind or inside the envelope and outflow of the Class 0 source Ser-SMM4. ⁽⁴⁾ Only one dither is used for channels 1 and 2 due to source lying at the edge of the FOV.

References. 1: Ortiz-León et al. (2018); 2: Karska et al. (2018); 3: Enoch et al. (2009). 4: Podio et al. (2021). 5: Ortiz-León et al. (2017). 6: Pontoppidan et al. (2004). 7: Krolikowski et al. (2021). 8: Seidensticker & Schmidt-Kaler (1989). 9: Tobin et al. (2019).

Fig. B.1. Extracted spectrum (top panel) and continuum images (bottom row) for B1-a-NS. The 12 subbands in the spectrum are not stitched, and each color represent one of the three MIRI-MRS gratings: A (red), B (black), and C (yellow). The bottom row shows from left to right the mid-IR continuum images around 5.3 μm (channel 1 short), 8.1 μm (channel 2 short), 12.5 μm (channel 3 short), and 19.3 μm (channel 4 short). The continuum images are scaled with a `sqrt` stretch to enhance fainter features without saturating brighter emission. A scale bar is displayed in the bottom right and the FWHM of the PSF is shown in the bottom right of each panel.

Fig. B.2. Same as Fig. B.1 but for B1-b.

Fig. B.3. Same as Fig. B.1 but for B1-c.

Fig. B.4. Same as Fig. B.1 but for IRAS 4B.

Fig. B.5. Same as Fig. B.1 but for L1448-mm.

Fig. B.6. Same as Fig. B.1 but for Per-emb 8.

Fig. B.7. Same as Fig. B.1 but for Ser-S68N-N.

Fig. B.8. Same as Fig. B.1 but for Ser-S68N-S.

Fig. B.9. Same as Fig. B.1 but for Ser-SMM1A.

Fig. B.10. Same as Fig. B.1 but for Ser-SMM1B.

Fig. B.11. Same as Fig. B.1 but for Ser-SMM3.

Fig. B.12. Same as Fig. B.1 but for SVS4-5.

Fig. B.13. Same as Fig. B.1 but for L1527.

Fig. B.14. Same as Fig. B.1 but for TMC1A.

Fig. B.15. Same as Fig. B.1 but for TMC1-E.

Fig. B.16. Same as Fig. B.1 but for TMC1-W.

Fig. B.17. Same as Fig. B.1 but for BHR71-IRS1.

Fig. B.18. Same as Fig. B.1 but for BHR71-IRS2.

Appendix C: Spectral information tables

In Table C.1, the noise estimates in units of mJy are presented. The noise level is estimated from line-free wavelength regions for each sub-band separately. For most sources, the noise level is about $\sim 0.1 - 0.5$ mJy in channels 1 – 3, whereas in channel 4 the noise levels increase toward several mJy in channels 4A and

4B and up to ~ 10 mJy in channel 4C. One major outlier is TMC1A where the noise levels are significantly higher. At the shorter wavelengths, this likely originates from the source lying on the very edge of the FOV, which hampers the sensitivity. At longer wavelengths, the noise levels are likely dominated by residual fringes at the 1% level of the continuum, which is several Jy in channels 3 and 4.

Table C.1. Noise level estimates (σ) in mJy derived from line-free wavelength regions per MIRI-MRS sub-band for all sources.

Source	σ_{1A}	σ_{1B}	σ_{1C}	σ_{2A}	σ_{2B}	σ_{2C}	σ_{3A}	σ_{3B}	σ_{3C}	σ_{4A}	σ_{4B}	σ_{4C}
	mJy											
B1-a-NS	0.36	0.40	0.40	0.49	0.37	0.60	0.52	0.73	0.69	2.49	4.33	11.85
B1-b	0.16	0.20	0.15	0.21	0.19	0.26	0.16	0.21	0.29	0.59	2.48	2.76
B1-c	0.40	0.17	0.49	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.08	0.30	2.43	2.33
L1448-mm	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.14	0.32	1.64	2.68
Per-emb8	0.17	0.18	0.14	0.17	0.13	0.16	0.10	0.13	0.15	0.42	0.95	2.20
Ser-S68N-N	0.11	0.11	0.08	0.12	0.07	0.11	0.08	0.11	0.15	0.39	0.79	1.76
Ser-SMM1A	0.14	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.29	0.85	4.74
Ser-SMM1B	0.09	0.06	0.02	0.07	0.06	0.10	0.08	0.07	0.11	0.25	1.11	2.88
Ser-SMM3	0.14	0.12	0.06	0.12	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.33	1.12	2.57
SVS4-5	0.32	0.14	0.28	0.27	0.25	0.31	0.63	0.78	0.61	1.82	2.61	4.10
L1527	0.35	0.22	0.18	0.22	0.24	0.24	0.14	0.13	0.14	0.46	0.95	1.52
TMC1A	14.5	3.68	7.53	6.58	3.71	3.68	8.03	9.10	7.16	8.66	16.9	30.0
TMC1-E	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.22	0.15	0.16	0.26	0.38	0.53	1.61	2.82	6.05
TMC1-W	0.31	0.36	0.33	0.26	0.49	0.34	0.34	0.35	0.71	1.66	2.02	5.46
BHR71-IRS1	0.69	0.28	0.42	0.16	0.16	0.15	0.10	0.21	0.29	1.49	3.43	9.69
BHR71-IRS2	0.12	0.18	0.13	0.13	0.16	0.20	0.15	0.13	0.15	0.55	1.12	2.04

Notes. No noise estimates are provided for IRAS 4B and Ser-S68N-S since no continuum source is detected.

Appendix D: Infrared pumping

The effect of infrared pumping is very dependent on both the rotational temperature T_{rot} and vibrational temperature T_{vib} . This is evident through the correction factor applied in Eq. (8), with both T_{rot} and T_{vib} present in an exponential. Moreover, also the wavelength (or frequency ν) through which the infrared pumping is thought to occur is very important.

In Fig. D.1, the correction factor (on logarithmic scale) to the number of molecules is presented as function of both T_{rot} and T_{vib} for three different wavelengths. It is clear that even small dif-

ferences in T_{vib} , which is estimated from the infrared brightness temperature via Eq. (7), can lead to several orders of magnitude differences in the correction factor to the number of molecules. This effect is strongest at shorter wavelengths and gets less pronounced when going to longer wavelengths, yet still the correction can be more than an order of magnitude. This thus results in large uncertainties on the number of molecules for species exhibiting emission with $T_{\text{vib}} > T_{\text{rot}}$. When $T_{\text{vib}} < T_{\text{rot}}$, no correction is applied since infrared pumping is likely not dominating the excitation.

Fig. D.1. Infrared pumping correction factor of Eq. (8) as function of T_{rot} and T_{vib} at $4.0 \mu\text{m}$ (left), $7.0 \mu\text{m}$ (middle), and $15.0 \mu\text{m}$ (right). The correction factor is presented on a logarithmic scale, with the black contours indicating orders of magnitude (up to 10^4). For the lower right of each panel where $T_{\text{vib}} < T_{\text{rot}}$, the correction factor is assumed to be 1 (i.e., no correction).

Appendix E: Importance of fitting optically thin and unblended lines

It is important to consider the optical depth of emission or absorption features in determining their physical parameters. The LTE slab models adopted in this paper do take line optical depth into account in determining the line strength (e.g., Tabone et al. 2023, see also Eq. (3)). Moreover, also the blending of multiple lines that remain unresolved at the spectral resolution of MIRI-MRS is taken into account. However, despite taking all these effects into account in LTE models, it remains important to fit weak optically thin transitions to derive the physical parameters such as the excitation temperature and column density.

Recently, Li et al. (2024) showed the importance of fitting only weak and unblended H₂O absorption features in JWST/MIRI-MRS data. Focusing mostly on absorption models of the rovibrational H₂O lines between 5 μ m and 8 μ m, they showed that the column density derived from these optically thick and often blended lines can lead to under- or over-estimating the column density by two orders of magnitude. For some of our sources, the fits between rotational and rovibrational lines agree very well (i.e., B1-c), but for others the difference in column densities is as large as two orders of magnitude despite similar excitation temperatures (B1-a-NS). This can also originate from IR pumping (higher N derived from rovibrational lines than from rotational lines) and or subthermal excitation (lower N derived from rovibrational lines than from rotational lines) but blending of rovibrational lines cannot be excluded. However, in this paper the main H₂O column used for abundance ratios is derived from pure rotational lines of H₂O at longer wavelengths for which line blending is less of an issue than for the rovibrational

lines. Line blending is therefore not affecting the total H₂O column densities derived in this work.

For other species, it is important to take line blending into account in fitting. This is most important for molecules showing emission or absorption through a Q -branch, which is the superposition of several transitions with $\Delta J = 0$ in a small wavelength region. These lines are spectrally unresolved at the spectral resolution of MIRI-MRS ($R \sim 3500 - 1000$; Labiano et al. 2021; Jones et al. 2023). In Fig. E.1, the best-fit LTE models to CO₂ in L1448-mm are presented for both cases of taking into account the Q -branch in the fit (top panel) and excluding it (bottom panel). Taking into account the Q -branch in the fit results in a significantly higher derived excitation temperature and an order of magnitude lower column density and number of molecules. However, the best-fit model depends highly on the shape of the Q -branch, which is very sensitive to the excitation temperature, but is also severely affected by blending of optically thick lines. In the bottom panel, the best-fit model excluding the Q -branch shows a much better fit to the R and P -branches and only underestimates the emission in the Q -branch by at most 30%. Moreover, the χ^2_{red} is significantly lower when the Q -branch is excluded and the derived excitation temperature is in perfect agreement with that of C₂H₂, HCN, and CH₄ (see Table 2), further supporting that the fit including the Q -branch is not correct. Furthermore, the number of molecules derived from CO₂ excluding the Q -branch is in perfect agreement with that derived from the ¹³CO₂ isotopologue multiplied by the ¹²C/¹³C ratio of the local ISM (70; Milam et al. 2005). This thus shows the importance of fitting unblended R and P -branch lines (if detected) in determining accurate excitation temperatures and column densities.

Fig. E.1. The best fit model of CO₂ (green) to the observed spectrum of L1448-mm (black) when the Q -branch around 15 μ m is included in the fit (top panel) and when it is excluded (bottom panel). The residuals of the fit are shown in gray in each panel. The best-fit parameters for both cases are presented in the top right of each panel. The best-fit parameters can differ significantly depending on whether the optically thick and blended Q -branch is taken into account in the fit. Excluding the Q -branch leads to more reliable derived quantities, see main text.

Appendix F: Residuals of LTE fits to B1-c

In Figs. F.1-F.4, the residuals to the best-fit LTE models are presented for our most line-rich source, B1-c. The residuals are plotted using a smaller scale on the y-axis, but are typically on the

level of 10-20%. In some cases the residuals indicate that a second temperature component could be present for some species. Alternatively, the residual lines could also originate from species not explored in this work.

Fig. F.1. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models (overlaid in red) for B1c in the 4.9 – 7.2 μm range. The residual to the fit is presented in gray in the panel above each spectrum, where it is important to note that the scale of the y-axis is different (smaller). Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel.

Fig. F.2. Same as Fig. F.1 but in the 7.2 – 13.0 μm range. The residual spectrum appears at this wavelength range is more noisy due to the deep silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. F.3. Same as Fig. F.1 but in the 13.0 – 16.5 μm range. The *P*-branch lines of CO₂ are completely extinguished by the CO₂ ice absorption feature.

Fig. F.4. Same as Fig. F.1 but in the 16.5 – 27.5 μm range.

Appendix G: LTE model fits to full spectra

In Figs. G.1-G.32, the full baseline-subtracted spectra are presented for all sources. The full best-fit LTE model is overlaid

as the red shaded region and each species contributing at the LTE model is presented below the observed spectrum. The physical parameters derived from the LTE fits are tabulated in Appendix H.

Fig. G.1. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for B1-a-NS in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H_2 and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.2. Same as Fig. G.1 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.3. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for B1-b in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.4. Same as Fig. G.3 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.5. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for B1-c in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.6. Same as Fig. G.5 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.7. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for L1448-mm in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.8. Same as Fig. G.7 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.9. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for Per-emb 8 in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9–13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.10. Same as Fig. G.9 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.11. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for Ser-S68N-N in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9–13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.12. Same as Fig. G.11 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.13. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for Ser-SMM1A in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.14. Same as Fig. G.13 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.15. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for Ser-SMM1B in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9–13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.16. Same as Fig. G.15 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.17. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for Ser-SMM3 in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9–13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.18. Same as Fig. G.17 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

SVS4-5

Fig. G.19. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for SVS4-5 in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9–13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.20. Same as Fig. G.19 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.21. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for L1527 in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H_2 and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.22. Same as Fig. G.21 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.23. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for TMC1A in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9–13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.24. Same as Fig. G.23 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.25. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for TMC1-E in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.26. Same as Fig. G.25 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.27. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for TMC1-W in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.28. Same as Fig. G.27 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.29. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for BHR71-IRS1 in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H₂ and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

Fig. G.30. Same as Fig. G.29 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Fig. G.31. Baseline-subtracted spectrum (black) and best-fit LTE models for BHR71-IRS2 in the 4.9 – 13 μm range. In each panel, the red shaded spectrum overlaid on top of the observed spectrum is the full best-fit LTE model. Each molecule contributing to this wavelength range is shown at an arbitrary constant offset in the bottom of each panel. Strong H_2 and atomic emission lines are labeled. The spectrum in the 9 – 13 μm wavelength range is more noisy due to the strong silicate and water libration mode absorption.

BHR71-IRS2

Fig. G.32. Same as Fig. G.31 but now for the 13 – 27.5 μm range.

Appendix H: Additional tables

Table H.1 indicates which molecule is detected in emission (E) or absorption (A) toward which sources. Tables H.2-H.17 present the derived excitation temperatures T_{ex} and column den-

sities N of the best-fit LTE models, as well as the emitting area (R_{em}) and number of molecules N_{mol} for emission models. For the latter, also the range N_{corr} is given when IR pumping is taken into account. Upper limits are presented for molecules that are not detected.

Table H.1. Presence of molecules in absorption (A), emission (E), or a non-detection (–).

Source	H ₂ O		CO ₂	¹³ CO ₂	C ₂ H ₂	¹³ CCH ₂	HCN	C ₄ H ₂	CH ₄	SO ₂	CS	SiO	NH ₃	CO	OH
	rot	rovib													
B1-a-NS	E	E	A	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	E	E
B1-b	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
B1-c	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	–	A	A	A	–	A	A	–
L1448-mm	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	–	E	–	E	E
IRAS 4B ⁽¹⁾	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Per-emb8	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Ser-S68N-N	E	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Ser-S68N-S ⁽¹⁾	E ⁽²⁾	–	E ⁽³⁾	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Ser-SMM1A	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Ser-SMM1B	–	A	E	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	A	–
Ser-SMM3	–	–	E	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
SVS4-5	E	E	E	–	–	–	–	–	E	–	–	–	–	E	E
L1527	–	E	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
TMC1A	–	A	A	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	E
TMC1-E	E ⁽⁴⁾	A	E	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	E	E
TMC1-W	E ⁽⁴⁾	E	E	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	E	E
BHR71-IRS1	E	A	A	–	A	–	–	–	–	–	–	A	–	A	E
BHR71-IRS2	–	A	E	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

Notes. ⁽¹⁾ No continuum from protostar detected across the full MIRI wavelength range. ⁽²⁾ Detected but likely originates from Ser-S68N-N. ⁽³⁾ Detected but is clearly associated with the outflow rather than the central protostellar position. ⁽⁴⁾ The binary components of TMC1 are indistinguishable at longer wavelengths.

Table H.2. LTE slab model results for B1-a-NS.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	160 ± 10	1.9 ± 0.5 × 10 ¹⁸	25 ± 1	7.9 ± 0.4 × 10 ⁴⁷	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	370 ± 10	4.4 ± 1.2 × 10 ¹⁹	2.3 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1 × 10 ⁴⁷	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	Y	-15	4.71	405 ± 15	1.9 ± 0.5 × 10 ¹⁷	2.6 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 1.1 × 10 ⁴⁴	153	–
CO ₂	A	Y	35	2.0	115 ± 25	7.8 ± 2.2 × 10 ¹⁵	–	–	–	–
¹³ CO ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.3 × 10 ¹⁵	–	–	–	–
C ₂ H ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.0 × 10 ¹⁵	–	–	–	–
¹³ CCH ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.8 × 10 ¹⁴	–	–	–	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.3 × 10 ¹⁶	[10]	< 9.4 × 10 ⁴⁴	137	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.8 × 10 ¹⁵	[10]	< 1.3 × 10 ⁴⁴	124	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 3.2 × 10 ¹⁷	[10]	< 2.2 × 10 ⁴⁶	128	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.0 × 10 ²¹	[10]	< 7.0 × 10 ⁴⁹	132	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.0 × 10 ²¹	[10]	< 7.0 × 10 ⁴⁹	124	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.0 × 10 ²¹	[10]	< 7.0 × 10 ⁴⁹	122	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 5.6 × 10 ¹⁶	[10]	< 4.0 × 10 ⁴⁵	151	< 3.2 × 10 ⁴⁵

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 7.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of B1-a-NS. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.3. LTE slab model results for B1-b.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 3.2 × 10 ¹⁷	[10]	< 2.2 × 10 ⁴⁶	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	< 3.2 × 10 ¹⁵	[10]	< 2.2 × 10 ⁴⁴	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 5.6 × 10 ²⁰	[10]	< 4.0 × 10 ⁴⁹	146	–
CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 3.2 × 10 ¹⁵	[10]	< 2.2 × 10 ⁴⁴	195	< 1.2 × 10 ⁴²
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 5.6 × 10 ¹⁵	[10]	< 4.0 × 10 ⁴⁴	195	< 2.2 × 10 ⁴²
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.8 × 10 ¹⁵	[10]	< 1.3 × 10 ⁴⁴	118	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 2.4 × 10 ¹⁵	[10]	< 1.7 × 10 ⁴⁴	118	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 2.4 × 10 ¹⁵	[10]	< 1.7 × 10 ⁴⁴	128	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 4.2 × 10 ¹⁴	[10]	< 3.0 × 10 ⁴³	114	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 3.2 × 10 ¹⁷	[10]	< 2.2 × 10 ⁴⁶	119	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.3 × 10 ¹⁷	[10]	< 9.4 × 10 ⁴⁵	123	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 4.2 × 10 ¹⁸	[10]	< 3.0 × 10 ⁴⁷	115	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.0 × 10 ¹⁸	[10]	< 7.0 × 10 ⁴⁶	113	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.8 × 10 ¹⁶	[10]	< 1.3 × 10 ⁴⁵	144	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 6.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of B1-b. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.4. LTE slab model results for B1-c.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 2.4 × 10 ¹⁷	–	–	–	–
warm H ₂ O	A	Y	6 ± 4	2.0	325 ± 15	4.4 ± 1.2 × 10 ¹⁸	–	–	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	A	Y	-1 ± 4	10.0	300 ± 10	7.8 ± 2.2 × 10 ¹⁸	–	–	–	–
CO ₂	A	Y	5 ± 4	10.0	330 ± 10	3.3 ± 0.9 × 10 ¹⁷	–	–	–	–
¹³ CO ₂	A	Y	0	4.71	225 ± 35	1.4 ± 0.4 × 10 ¹⁶	–	–	–	–
C ₂ H ₂	A	Y	0	4.71	285 ± 25	1.9 ± 0.5 × 10 ¹⁷	–	–	–	–
¹³ CCH ₂	A	Y	0	2.0	100 ± 20	5.9 ± 1.6 × 10 ¹⁵	–	–	–	–
HCN	A	Y	0	4.71	180 ± 10	3.3 ± 0.9 × 10 ¹⁷	–	–	–	–
C ₄ H ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 5.6 × 10 ¹⁴	–	–	–	–
CH ₄	A	Y	0	2.0	200 ± 10	4.4 ± 1.2 × 10 ¹⁷	–	–	–	–
SO ₂	A	Y	0	2.0	150 ± 10	5.9 ± 1.6 × 10 ¹⁶	–	–	–	–
CS	A	Y	0	2.0	285 ± 15	2.5 ± 0.7 × 10 ¹⁷	–	–	–	–
SiO	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 2.4 × 10 ¹⁶	–	–	–	–
NH ₃	A	Y	0	4.71	340 ± 10	1.9 ± 0.5 × 10 ¹⁷	–	–	–	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was computed using Gaussian models to selected unblended lines for H₂O and CO₂ and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 6.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of B1-c. For all other species, v_{line} was determined through visual inspection. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.5. LTE slab model results for L1448-mm.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	Y	-25 ± 3	4.71	130 ± 10	2.5 ± 0.7 × 10 ¹⁸	44 ± 2	3.3 ± 0.2 × 10 ⁴⁸	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	Y	-25 ± 3	4.71	390 ± 10	7.8 ± 2.2 × 10 ¹⁷	2.3 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.2 × 10 ⁴⁵	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	Y	-12 ± 3	4.71	180 ± 10	4.4 ± 1.2 × 10 ¹⁷	59 ± 2	1.1 ± 0.1 × 10 ⁴⁸	143	–
CO ₂	E	Y	2 ± 2	4.71	120 ± 10	7.8 ± 2.2 × 10 ¹⁷	37 ± 1	7.3 ± 0.4 × 10 ⁴⁷	187	3.1 × 10 ⁴³ –7.3 × 10 ⁴⁷
¹³ CO ₂	E	Y	0	4.71	[120]	< 1.8 × 10 ¹⁵	244 ± 150	1.1 ± 0.1 × 10 ⁴⁶	187	4.7 × 10 ⁴¹ –1.1 × 10 ⁴⁶
C ₂ H ₂	E	Y	0	4.71	110 ± 10	1.4 ± 0.4 × 10 ¹⁷	49 ± 11	2.5 ± 1.1 × 10 ⁴⁷	118	4.3 × 10 ⁴⁶ –3.6 × 10 ⁴⁷
¹³ CCH ₂	E	Y	0	4.71	[110]	< 3.2 × 10 ¹⁵	128 ± 87	3.5 ± 0.2 × 10 ⁴⁵	118	1.0 × 10 ⁴⁵ –3.6 × 10 ⁴⁵
HCN	E	Y	0	4.71	110 ± 10	1.4 ± 0.4 × 10 ¹⁶	83 ± 4	6.5 ± 0.3 × 10 ⁴⁶	127	5.3 × 10 ⁴⁵ –6.5 × 10 ⁴⁶
C ₄ H ₂	E	Y	0	4.71	[100]	< 2.4 × 10 ¹⁵	112 ± 72	2.5 ± 0.1 × 10 ⁴⁵	114	2.4 × 10 ⁴⁴ –2.7 × 10 ⁴⁵
CH ₄	E	Y	0	4.71	130 ± 10	7.8 ± 2.2 × 10 ¹⁶	213 ± 10	2.1 ± 0.1 × 10 ⁴⁸	119	–
SO ₂	E	Y	-25	4.71	140 ± 20	< 1.0 × 10 ¹⁷	1.5 ± 1.4 × 10 ³	3.6 ± 3.5 × 10 ⁴⁷	122	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.3 × 10 ¹⁹	[10]	< 9.4 × 10 ⁴⁷	115	–
SiO	E	Y	-24 ± 2	4.71	310 ± 10	3.3 ± 0.9 × 10 ¹⁷	1.9 ± 0.3	6.9 ± 1.5 × 10 ⁴⁴	113	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	< 1.8 × 10 ¹⁷	[10]	< 1.3 × 10 ⁴⁶	141	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was computed using Gaussian models to selected unblended lines for H₂O, CO₂, and SiO and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 5.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of L1448-mm. For all other species, v_{line} was determined through visual inspection. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.6. LTE slab model results for Per-emb 8.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{18}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{46}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{44}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	132	–
CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{45}$	181	$< 3.4 \times 10^{43}$
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{44}$	181	$< 1.4 \times 10^{43}$
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{43}$	105	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{44}$	105	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{44}$	114	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{44}$	101	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{46}$	106	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{45}$	110	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{18}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{46}$	102	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{18}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{46}$	100	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{45}$	130	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 11.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of Per-emb8. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.7. LTE slab model results for Ser-S68N-N.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	200 ± 10	$< 4.2 \times 10^{17}$	15 ± 4	$3.1 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{46}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{44}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	143	–
CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{44}$	178	$< 3.6 \times 10^{42}$
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{44}$	178	$< 1.1 \times 10^{43}$
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{43}$	117	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{43}$	117	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{44}$	126	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{43}$	113	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{18}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{46}$	118	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{46}$	122	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{20}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{49}$	114	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{19}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{47}$	112	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{46}$	141	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 8.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of Ser-S68N-N. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.8. LTE slab model results for Ser-SMM1A.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{19}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{48}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{44}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	134	–
CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{45}$	15	–
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{46}$	15	–
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{45}$	113	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{44}$	113	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{44}$	121	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{44}$	110	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	114	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{18}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{47}$	117	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	110	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	109	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	133	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 8.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of Ser-SMM1A. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.9. LTE slab model results for Ser-SMM1B.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{45}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{44}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	A	Y	10	2.0	980 ± 20	$2.3 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{18}$	–	–	–	–
CO ₂	E	Y	10	4.71	205 ± 25	$< 1.8 \times 10^{16}$	110 ± 97	$2.2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^{45}$	15	–
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{45}$	15	–
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{44}$	118	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{44}$	118	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{44}$	129	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{44}$	114	–
CH ₄	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{44}$	124	–
CS	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{16}$	–	–	–	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{46}$	112	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{46}$	146	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 8.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of Ser-SMM1B. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.10. LTE slab model results for Ser-SMM3.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{46}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{44}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	136	–
CO ₂	E	Y	0	4.71	90 ± 10	$< 7.5 \times 10^{15}$	$1.1 \pm 0.9 \times 10^3$	$2.9 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{47}$	180	$2.3 \times 10^{39} - 3.1 \times 10^{47}$
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{44}$	180	$< 1.2 \times 10^{43}$
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{44}$	109	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{44}$	109	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{44}$	119	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{43}$	106	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{18}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{47}$	111	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{46}$	115	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{19}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{47}$	106	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	105	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{46}$	134	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 8.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of Ser-SMM3. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.11. LTE slab model results for SVS4-5.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	210 ± 10	$< 3.2 \times 10^{17}$	332 ± 318	$3.3 \pm 1.1 \times 10^{46}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	515 ± 15	$1.9 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{19}$	1.8 ± 0.1	$4.9 \pm 0.8 \times 10^{46}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	1040 ± 20	$2.3 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{18}$	0.5 ± 0.1	$4.3 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{44}$	170	–
CO ₂	E	Y	-80	4.71	[200]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{17}$	5.3 ± 1.7	$2.4 \pm 1.5 \times 10^{45}$	220	$1.7 \times 10^{44} - 3.9 \times 10^{45}$
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{45}$	220	$< 1.3 \times 10^{42}$
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{45}$	138	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{44}$	138	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{44}$	149	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{43}$	134	–
CH ₄	E	Y	-40	4.71	460 ± 80	$< 5.6 \times 10^{16}$	44 ± 42	$3.5 \pm 1.9 \times 10^{44}$	140	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	144	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	133	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{21}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{49}$	133	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{45}$	167	$< 1.8 \times 10^{45}$

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 8.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of SVS4-5. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.12. LTE slab model results for L1527.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{45}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{43}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	90 ± 10	$< 4.2 \times 10^{16}$	$1.3 \pm 1.2 \times 10^5$	$7.1 \pm 7.0 \times 10^{52}$	132	$8.2 \times 10^{46} - 1.4 \times 10^{53}$
CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{43}$	15	–
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{43}$	15	–
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{42}$	106	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{43}$	106	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{43}$	115	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{42}$	102	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{45}$	107	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{45}$	111	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{45}$	103	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{45}$	101	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{45}$	130	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 5.9 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of L1527. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.13. LTE slab model results for TMC1A.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{17}$	–	–	–	–
warm H ₂ O	A	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{16}$	–	–	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	A	Y	-20	20.0	440 ± 10	$1.4 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{17}$	–	–	–	–
CO ₂	A	Y	0	2.0	60 ± 10	$1.4 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{16}$	–	–	–	–
¹³ CO ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–
C ₂ H ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{14}$	–	–	–	–
¹³ CCH ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{14}$	–	–	–	–
HCN	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{14}$	–	–	–	–
C ₄ H ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{14}$	–	–	–	–
CH ₄	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–
SO ₂	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–
CS	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–
SiO	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–
NH ₃	A	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 6.6 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of TMC1A. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.14. LTE slab model results for TMC1-E.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	185 ± 15	$< 4.2 \times 10^{17}$	155 ± 150	$8.4 \pm 5.1 \times 10^{45}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	405 ± 15	$1.0 \pm 0.3 \times 10^{20}$	0.5 ± 0.1	$1.5 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{46}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	A	Y	-20	2.0	580 ± 20	$1.0 \pm 0.3 \times 10^{17}$	–	–	–	–
CO ₂	E	Y	0	4.71	315 ± 25	$< 1.3 \times 10^{17}$	0.8 ± 0.2	$2.9 \pm 1.3 \times 10^{43}$	212	–
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{43}$	212	$< 1.0 \times 10^{41}$
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{43}$	137	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{43}$	137	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{43}$	146	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{42}$	133	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{45}$	138	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 7.5 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 5.3 \times 10^{44}$	142	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{44}$	133	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{45}$	132	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{44}$	162	$< 5.0 \times 10^{43}$

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 5.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of TMC1-E. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.15. LTE slab model results for TMC1-W.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	190 ± 10	$< 5.6 \times 10^{17}$	6.4 ± 1.9	$5.7 \pm 2.1 \times 10^{45}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	485 ± 15	$4.4 \pm 1.2 \times 10^{19}$	0.3 ± 0.1	$2.6 \pm 0.6 \times 10^{45}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	E	Y	0	4.71	1180 ± 20	$1.1 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{20}$	0.06 ± 0.10	$2.3 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{44}$	180	–
CO ₂	E	Y	0	4.71	190 ± 10	$1.9 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{18}$	1.1 ± 0.1	$1.8 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{45}$	236	$2.9 \times 10^{43} - 2.7 \times 10^{45}$
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{43}$	236	$< 8.3 \times 10^{39}$
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 1.7 \times 10^{43}$	148	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{42}$	148	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{43}$	159	$< 9.8 \times 10^{42}$
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{42}$	143	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{18}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{46}$	149	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 7.0 \times 10^{45}$	154	$< 4.8 \times 10^{45}$
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{46}$	144	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{46}$	142	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{44}$	177	$< 1.9 \times 10^{43}$

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = 5.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of TMC1-W. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.16. LTE slab model results for BHR71-IRS1.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	Y	-42 ± 3	4.71	140 ± 10	$3.3 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{18}$	24 ± 1	$1.3 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{48}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{44}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	A	Y	-44 ± 9	10.0	560 ± 10	$5.9 \pm 1.6 \times 10^{18}$	–	–	–	–
CO ₂	A	Y	-10 ± 4	10.0	260 ± 10	$3.3 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{16}$	–	–	–	–
¹³ CO ₂	A	N	–	10.0	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{14}$	–	–	–	–
C ₂ H ₂	A	Y	-5	10.0	[150]	$1.0 \pm 0.3 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–
¹³ CCH ₂	A	N	–	10.0	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{14}$	–	–	–	–
HCN	A	N	–	10.0	[150]	$< 1.0 \times 10^{15}$	–	–	–	–
C ₄ H ₂	A	N	–	10.0	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{14}$	–	–	–	–
CH ₄	A	N	–	10.0	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{16}$	–	–	–	–
SO ₂	A	N	–	10.0	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{16}$	–	–	–	–
CS	A	N	–	10.0	[150]	$< 2.4 \times 10^{16}$	–	–	–	–
SiO	A	Y	-23 ± 2	4.71	400 ± 20	$1.9 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{18}$	–	–	–	–
NH ₃	A	N	–	10.0	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{16}$	–	–	–	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was computed using Gaussian models to selected unblended lines for H₂O, CO₂, and SiO and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = -4.7 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of BHR71-IRS1. For all other species, v_{line} was determined through visual inspection. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.

Table H.17. LTE slab model results for BHR71-IRS2.

Species	Mode	Detected	v_{line} (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	T_{ex} (K)	N (cm ⁻²)	R_{em} (au)	N_{mol}	T_{IR} (K)	N_{corr}
cold H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 4.2 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 3.0 \times 10^{46}$	–	–
warm H ₂ O	E	N	–	4.71	[450]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{44}$	–	–
rovib H ₂ O	A	Y	-45	4.71	440 ± 40	$1.4 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{19}$	–	–	–	–
CO ₂	E	Y	0	4.71	75 ± 15	$3.3 \pm 2.3 \times 10^{17}$	541 ± 466	$1.8 \pm 1.7 \times 10^{50}$	173	$4.4 \times 10^{36} - 3.6 \times 10^{50}$
¹³ CO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{45}$	173	$< 6.1 \times 10^{43}$
C ₂ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{43}$	107	–
¹³ CCH ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 9.4 \times 10^{43}$	107	–
HCN	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{15}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{44}$	116	–
C ₄ H ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{14}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{43}$	103	–
CH ₄	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{45}$	108	–
SO ₂	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{17}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{46}$	112	–
CS	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 5.6 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 4.0 \times 10^{45}$	104	–
SiO	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 3.2 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 2.2 \times 10^{45}$	102	–
NH ₃	E	N	–	4.71	[150]	$< 1.8 \times 10^{16}$	[10]	$< 1.3 \times 10^{45}$	130	–

Notes. Square brackets indicate that the parameter was fixed. The second column indicates whether the molecular features were fitted using an absorption (A) or emission (E) model. The velocity v_{line} was determined through visual inspection and is with respect to the $v_{\text{lsr}} = -4.7 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of BHR71-IRS2. The last column shows the range in total number of molecules corrected for IR pumping using Eq. (8) when $T_{\text{IR}} > T_{\text{ex}}$.